

BENEFITS OF LEARNING NEW LANGUAGES FOR YOUNG PEOPLE

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Abstract. *This article will be about languages which are learning over the world and its bright sights for people themselves, society as well. Moreover, It will lead to fields that are developing by exchanging experience between prestigious universities of countries, organizations, companies. Besides, article will give information and facts about how languages can help to change people's mind in wide range of fields of society.*

Keywords: IELTS, TOFEL, IT, AI, lingua franca, United Kingdom, United State.

Annotatsiya. *Bu maqolada dunyo boyicha keng o'rganilayotgan tillar hamda ularning insonlar va jamiyat uchun bo'lgan bir talay foydalari haqida so'z boradi. Bundan tashqari, xalqaro nufuzli universitetlar, tashkilotlar va kompaniyalar o'rtasidagi tajriba almashinuvi turli xil sohalarning rivojiga yetaklaydi. Shuning bilan birga, maqola davomida insonlarning dunyo qarashi, jamiyatning turli xil sohalarida o'zgarganligi haqida ham ma'lumotlar berib o'tiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: IELTS, TOFEL, IT, AI, lingua franca, United Kingdom, United State.

Аннотация. *Эта статья будет о языках, которые изучают во всем мире, и о том, что это яркое зрелище для самих людей, общества в том числе. Более того, это приведет к направлениям, которые развиваются путём обмена опытом между престижными университетами стран, организаций, компаний. Кроме того, в статье будет представлена информация и факты о том, как языки могут помочь изменить сознание людей в самых разных сферах жизни общества.*

Ключевые слова: IELTS, TOFEL, IT, AI, lingua franca, United Kingdom, United State.

INTRODUCTION. Nowadays, most languages are really popular around the world and countries which are accepted languages in a formal way that are popular as well. As an example to well-known foreign languages I can write English, Russian,

Italian, Arabic, French, Mandarin Chinese, German, Spanish and so on. Countries of international languages that are given above are really developed and industrialized. Such as Russia, America, Italy, Arab countries, France. In that fast pace modern world most young people who want to make successful future career usually learn foreign languages and some modern technologies like IT, AI and robots that are made for leading easy life. Learning foreign languages typically open different doors of the world in order to develop various fields. These days statistics and facts show that most people worldwide approximately 1.5 billion people are currently learning foreign languages. For example English, as a result it receives as an international language. When it comes to information of English language and its official places that language is used.

English language has a big history influenced by different languages such as Germanic French and Latin languages. It is popular with beautiful fluency, its extensive vocabulary, about 170,000 words used recently by most people. English grammar includes a subject-verb-object word order and verb conjugation and tenses that are complex system. According to place that language is used by communication of people English is West Germanic language which originated in England and nowadays spoken as a first or second language over the world. It is the official language of various countries which are New Zealand, the United States, United Kingdom, Australia and Canada. English is widely used among people for international communication as a lingua franca in wide range of fields such as science, business, technology and entertainment. English language has become dominant language in many fields of global communication due to effect of the United States and British Empire as a global superpower. There are different types of English, such as American English, Canadian English, Australian English and British English. These variations usually differ in vocabulary, pronunciation and spelling conventions. In such areas of the world tests are organized for checking knowledge in English language. For example, TOEFL, and IELTS (International English Language Testing System). These tests give access to check several skills in English

Including speaking, writing, listening, reading of individuals.

METHODS. Nowadays, most youngsters try really hard in order to learn how to speak foreign language, and how to write essay easier, and faster by reading many learning methods, and rules. Let's look English language as an example, for learning different languages, government create, and develop various opportunities for young people. For example in many educational areas such as school, collage, lyceum, university and English-speaking clubs which are changed with rebuilding, and bringing professional teachers like or native speakers. It is a great chance for young people to

create successful future career. As for as teaching methods of experts, they usually speak in a foreign language to teach faster, and to make foreign atmosphere. I think this method plays crucial role in learning process. Because during the lesson students can easily learn how to speak fluently, and they are highly likely motivated by lessons. The courses that involving classroom learning, and online course. When it comes to classroom course, students usually go and speak about different topics as a consequence they exchange ideas of each other. Moreover, online course is also beneficial for keeping precious time that students spend during coming by bus or private vehicle, and it gives great chance to learn with advancement technology, online learning courses are becoming increasingly popular worldwide. These courses often offer to learners flexibility in terms of location and time, allowing students to access materials that are given during the lesson at their own pace. However, most students prefer studying at traditional learning course so that they easily identify theme that they do not understand. It usually involves many activities such as interactive activities, feedback from teacher, group discussion as well. What's more immersion programs that involve living in a country which should speak in English language or English community where people accept English as a primary language. In most cases this method offers an immersion experience, it is access for learners to practice, and learn English in real-life situation also improve students' fluency through communicating with foreigners.

Another beneficial method is reading English books such as newspapers, and magazines. Reading that kind of books expose learners to wide range of writing styles,

academic vocabulary, and complex grammar structures. It always helps to learners to develop reading comprehension and vocabulary range. Furthermore, self-study that means learning language independently by reading different English books, and listening BBC learning English, podcasts, online resources that are usually given in channels of foreign teachers. Finally, one of the popular methods on is joining online courses or speaking clubs, watching foreign movies in their original language. In most times, they help learners to improve their pronunciation, speaking, and it teaches them how to make sentences correctly.

RESULTS. These days learning different international languages by young people result on developing political economy and society. Firstly, economic growth: learning international languages can open up different doors of opportunities for tourism, trade, and business partnership with companies over the world. It can easily attract people who are foreign investigators and rise exports for contributing to growth of economy. Moreover, it can result on reducing unemployment rate. Because proficiency in such fields which are in foreign languages can improve employ-ability namely in industries like international relations, costumer service, hospitality and tourism. This can help to reduce unemployment rates and income that is higher than before. As well as learning new languages leads to cultural exchange. Nowadays, most young people are interested in learning foreign languages and studying abroad, they easily make way for their interests about lifestyle of foreigners, national foods, behavior, how they respect their family, national values. As a consequence youngsters go abroad and life there, after that they begin boosting their cultures to foreigner as well. Additionally, it is also beneficial for enhancing communication over the world. People who are learned foreign language they can communicate with foreigners and even solve in particular global problems such as global warming, climate change, health crises, poverty and unemployment rate. Furthermore, knowing foreign language usually gives to learners access for watching movies of another country and reading story books in English or other languages. Also, it results on personal development. Because people who are learning foreign language, they read at least a hundred books that are about life of another countries and values of them.

DISCUSSION. Nowadays learning foreign languages is the most common factor of globalization. Many people who learn foreign language for many reasons. For example people learn international language the reason why they want to change the world that they live. Because it mostly leads to learning different new things worldwide, comprehensive and well-rounded experience. Such as new culture, new foreign friends, new wearing style, national food of them, exchanging cultural heritage, developing new fields in companies and I think it easily leads to globalization over the

world. In my opinion it plays crucial role for some countries that do not develop very well in such ways. For example tourism, international relations like international business partnerships, medical service, export and import.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion there are several fields that we saw above, they are invented by learning foreign languages such as English, Russian, French, Italian, German, Arabic and others in that modern world. As a consequence, its results are really effective to society and political economy. Moreover, it is useful for personal development, so people spend their precious time to read many books that are in foreign languages. By reading them people can easily learn different new things about new culture, communication with new friends, travel to foreign sightseeing places.

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